

Thymoquinone attenuates central neuropathic pain in experimental diabetes

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Abstract

This study aims to assess the ameliorative effects of thymoquinone on thermal nociception and diabetes-related cerebral cortex damage. Twenty-four adult rats were randomly assigned to four groups: control, untreated diabetic, and diabetic groups administered thymoquinone (TQ) at 25 mg/kg and 50 mg/kg daily for 6 weeks. Malondialdehyde (MDA) was quantified, and tail immersion and hot-plate tests were used to assess the animals' pain sensitivity, followed by obtaining samples of the brain for cerebral cortex histopathological analysis. Rats in the untreated group had higher MDA levels, and they felt pain earlier than healthy rats. In treated groups, TQ significantly decreased MDA and extended nociceptive latency. Histological analysis validated that TQ conferred significant protection against cerebral cortical injury. In conclusion, TQ significantly reduces oxidative stress, ameliorates nociceptive impairment, and provides protection against cerebral cortical damage in diabetic model rodents.

Keywords

cerebral cortex, diabetes mellitus, nociceptive, oxidative stress, thymoquinone

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a metabolic disorder that affects multiple organ systems. In addition to the prevalent peripheral nervous system (PNS) complications observed in diabetic patients, diabetes also adversely affects the central nervous system (CNS) (Rashedinia et al. 2020). While diabetic peripheral neuropathy has been widely documented, research investigating diabetes-related changes in the central nervous system is currently limited (Elgayar 2017). Persistent hyperglycaemia can cause serious problems in diverse organs, including the central nervous system, which can result in diabetic encephalopathy. It is widely recognised that DM is linked to cognitive impairments and an elevated likelihood of dementia, stroke, cerebro-

vascular disease, and Alzheimer's disease, in addition to mental health conditions such as depression (Riederer et al. 2017; Hameed et al. 2025).

Cognitive deficits are more pronounced in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus, even though type 2 diabetes mellitus is more prevalent in the general population (Smolina et al. 2015). It has been demonstrated that diabetic patients exhibit white matter lesions in the frontal cortex, which trigger neuronal damage, increase apoptotic cell counts, impair cognitive function, and cause oxidative stress. Furthermore, pro-inflammatory cytokines have higher plasma concentrations in diabetic patients, which can exacerbate inflammation (Baptista et al. 2020). Damage to the cerebral cortex in diabetic model (DM) rats can significantly affect nociceptive processing, the

brain's mechanism for encoding and responding to harmful stimuli. The cerebral cortex, especially the primary somatosensory cortex, insular cortex, and anterior cingulate cortex, is very important for how we feel and experience pain. Damage to these areas can alter the normal processing of nociceptive signals, potentially altering how pain is felt and how people respond to it (Pellicer et al. 2022).

Although insulin and hypoglycaemic medications continue to be the most common treatments, new approaches to both preventing and managing complications from diabetes have been studied. New antioxidants that could serve as a prospective treatment modality for mitigating and managing neurological injury are currently being identified through research conducted in experimental models of diabetes (Louzada and Vargas 2015).

Medicinal plants have been widely employed in the management of several neurodegenerative disorders and offer numerous benefits, including minimal side effects, widespread availability, and ease of administration.

Thymoquinone (TQ) is a major constituent of *Nigella sativa* (NS), often referred to as black seed or cummin, which is classified as an annual plant and belongs to the Ranunculaceae family (Farkhondeh et al. 2018). Thymoquinone is a well-recognised natural compound used both traditionally and therapeutically. It possesses many pharmacological characteristics, including antibacterial, antihistamine, antioxidant, immunomodulatory, and anticancer actions. TQ has protective effects against oxidative stress, inflammation, and diabetes; it may have clinical effects against a number of disorders due to its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. It can scavenge radicals and enter subcellular compartments despite physiological barriers (Tabassum et al. 2021).

Method

Animals

Twenty-four mature female Wistar rats, weighing 200–250 g, were randomly selected from the university's animal house. Animals had a one-week acclimatisation phase at the animal facility prior to experimentation, residing in cages inside a room maintained under normal lighting conditions, with a 12-hour light–dark cycle at 25 ± 1 °C. They were supplied with water and a healthy standard diet. The animals were divided into four groups, with six rats per group. G1: healthy control (negative control); G2: diabetic rats (positive control); G3: DM rats treated with 25 mg/kg TQ; and G4: DM rats treated with 50 mg/kg TQ. To make the study design more reliable, randomisation and blinding were used. Using <https://www.randomizer.org>, a two-step randomisation was performed to choose healthy animals from a large pool. When it was confirmed that streptozotocin (STZ) caused diabetes (fasting blood glucose > 250 mg/dL), the same randomised method was

used to assign the diabetic rats to treatment groups (control and experimental). An unbiased investigator used a single-blind design to conceal the distribution. This procedure ensured that volunteers assessing outcomes did not know which group they were in, thereby making the results from the STZ-induced diabetic rat model more reliable and reducing bias.

Abbreviations

TQ: thymoquinone; MDA: malondialdehyde; DM: diabetes mellitus; PNS: peripheral nervous system; CNS: central nervous system; NS: *Nigella sativa*; STZ: streptozotocin; GSH: glutathione; CAT: catalase; SOD: superoxide dismutase; TRPV1: transient receptor potential vanilloid 1; NO: nitric oxide.

Induction of diabetes

The research involved four evenly distributed groups of rats, each with six rats ($N = 6$). Diabetes mellitus was induced in Groups 2, 3, and 4 with a single administration of streptozotocin (50 mg/kg body weight), dissolved in 5 mM citrate buffer at pH 4.5 (Lutfi et al. 2021; Ahmed et al. 2024). Control animals (Group 1) received an equal volume (1 mL) of the buffer alone. Fasting blood glucose levels were measured using a glucometer (VivaChek Biotech (Hangzhou) Co., China) 2 days after STZ injection. Rats were classified as DM if their blood glucose levels exceeded 250 mg/dL. Thereafter, all animals in the treatment groups began therapy 48 hours after diabetes induction.

Administration of the investigational medication

The healthy control rats in Group 1 and the untreated diabetic rats in Group 2 received no pharmacological therapies. Each group received 1 mL of distilled water per 100 g of body weight by oral gavage daily for 6 weeks. The rats in Group 1 exhibited good health. TQ powder was solubilised in corn oil, and the resulting TQ solution was administered once daily by gastric gavage for up to 6 weeks to Groups 3 and 4, which received 25 mg/kg and 50 mg/kg, respectively.

Anaesthesia and sample collection

To achieve anaesthetic induction, rats were given a combination of xylazine and ketamine intraperitoneally at doses of 10 mg/kg body weight and 75 mg/kg body weight, respectively. Five to six minutes later, anaesthesia was induced (Pennasilico et al. 2025). Following completion of the experiments and administration of anaesthesia, the desired organs were preserved for histopathological analysis, and blood samples were obtained for further biochemical analyses.

Table 1. Equipment, instruments, and kits used in the study.

Equipment	Model	Purpose
pH meter	WTW Germany	pH measurement of citrate buffer
VivaCheck glucometer	China	Blood glucose measurement
Sensitive balance	KERN ABS 120-4N Philippines	Weighing of drugs and chemical substances of buffer preparation
MDA ELISA kit	Sunlong, China	MDA assessment
Elisa machine	BioTek ELx808, USA	MDA absorbance measurement
Centrifuge	Jouan B4i, France	Preparation of serum
Light microscopy	Nikon Eclipse E200, Japan	Histological study
Thermometer	France	Temperature control for tail immersion and hot plate test

All equipment underwent standard laboratory quality control, and calibration and service records are maintained as required by the institution to ensure measurements can be traced.

Pain behavioural assessments (nociceptive)

Hot plate test

This experiment involves placing a rat in an open-ended cylindrical container with a metallic plate floor heated by an electrical current. The plate was kept at a constant temperature of 50 ± 1 °C, provoking two quantifiable behavioural reactions distinguished by their reaction times: paw-licking and jumping. Latency was assessed from the introduction of a rat to the first avoidance response, with a maximum of 20 seconds (Dizaye and Qadir 2014; Nahar et al. 2022).

Tail immersion test

The distal two-thirds of a rat's tail are usually immersed in a controlled water bath that is kept at a certain temperature for the tail immersion test. The primary sign is how long it takes for an animal to show a reflexive tail withdrawal, or "tail flick", after exposure to cold water. This is called tail-withdrawal latency; it is usually performed in a cold-water bath (4 ± 1 °C) to assess allodynia by measuring the time to tail withdrawal of the submerged tail end (maximum 20 seconds) (Udell et al. 2021).

Statistical analysis

All data are shown as means \pm standard error of the mean ($M \pm SEM$). SPSS version 26 was used to perform the statistical analysis. The Shapiro–Wilk and Levene's tests were used to assess whether the assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variances were met. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied to the data, and partial eta squared (η^2) was used to estimate the magnitude of the treatment effects. Duncan's New Multiple Range Test for post hoc comparisons was used to determine whether the treatment means differed. A p -value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Glycaemic and serum malondialdehyde (MDA) levels

The following were the blood glucose levels (mg/dL) after 6 weeks: the mean glucose level in Group 1 (control) was 94.50 ± 4.26 mg/dL. The mean glucose level in Group 2, which consisted of untreated diabetics, was 622.83 ± 7.25 mg/dL. The mean for Group 3 (treated group TQ25) was 472.83 ± 67.59 mg/dL, and the mean for Group 4 (treated group TQ50) was 302.83 ± 44.64 mg/dL (Table 2).

Malondialdehyde (MDA) levels, measured in ng/mL, were significantly higher in the positive control group (G2: 130.3 ± 1.25) than in the negative control group (G1: 26.43 ± 1.16 , $p < 0.05$) after 6 weeks. MDA levels (G3: 22.82 ± 2.58 ; G4: 26.73 ± 4.68) were significantly reduced after treatment with TQ at doses of 25 mg/kg and 50 mg/kg. This reduction was consistent with the levels seen in the negative control (Table 2).

Table 2. Glycaemic levels (mg/dL) and MDA levels (ng/mL) of rats in the control and treated groups after 6 weeks.

Parameter	Negative control G1	Positive control G2	TQ 25 mg/kg G3	TQ 50 mg/kg G4
Blood glucose mg/dL (after 6 weeks)	94.50 ± 4.264 a	622.83 ± 7.250 d	472.83 ± 67.59 c	302.83 ± 44.6 b
MDA ng/mL (after 6 weeks)	26.43 ± 1.16 a	130.3 ± 1.25 b	22.82 ± 2.58 a	26.73 ± 4.68 a

• Means followed by different letters are significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

Behavioural tests for thermal nociception

After 6 weeks of treatment, the tail immersion and hot-plate tests were used to assess the body's response to thermal pain.

In the tail-immersion test, the negative control group (G1) had a latency of 19.83 ± 0.167 seconds, which was much longer than that of the other groups. The diabetic group (positive control, G2) had a much shorter latency (6.5 ± 0.428 seconds; $p < 0.05$). When given thymoquinone (TQ) at a dose of 25 mg/kg (G3), there was a small increase in response latency (7.67 ± 2.41 seconds). At a dose of 50 mg/kg (G4), there was a larger increase in latency (12.25 ± 1.03 seconds) (Table 3).

Table 3. Behavioural tests for thermal nociception in rats, the control and experimental groups, after 6 weeks.

Parameter	Negative control G1	Positive control G2	TQ 25 mg/kg G3	TQ 50 mg/kg G4
Tail immersion (seconds) (after 6 weeks)	19.83 ± 0.167 c	6.5 ± 0.428 a	7.67 ± 2.41 a	12.25 ± 1.03 b
Hot plate (paw licking) (seconds) (after 6 weeks)	9.5 ± 0.56 c	3.0 ± 0.001 a	3.83 ± 0.79 a	5.67 ± 0.42 b
Hot plate (jumping) second (after 6 weeks)	20 ± 0.001 d	3.0 ± 0.516 a	7.67 ± 1.145 b	12.5 ± 1.648 c

• Means followed by different letters are significantly different at $p < 0.05$.

The hot plate test (licking response) showed that G2 had a much shorter latency time (3.0 ± 0.001 seconds) than G1 (9.5 ± 0.56 seconds; $p < 0.05$). The TQ-treated groups had longer latency times: G3, 3.83 ± 0.79 seconds; G4, 5.67 ± 0.42 seconds (Table 3).

The hot plate test (jumping response) showed that the G1 group had the longest latency (20 ± 0.001 seconds), while the G2 group had a large drop (3.0 ± 0.516 seconds). Giving TQ increased latency in a dose-dependent way, with groups G3 and G4 showing latencies of 7.67 ± 1.145 seconds and 12.5 ± 1.648 seconds, respectively (Table 3).

Histopathological study of the cerebral cortex

The histopathological results of Group 1, the healthy control, showed that the cerebral cortex is typically composed of large neurones with separate cell bodies and vesicular nuclei. The neuropil is intact and uniform, with small glial nuclei scattered throughout and normal blood vessels. There were no major histopathological alterations (score 0) (Fig. 1A).

The photomicrograph for Group 2 (positive group) shows scattered pyknotic neurones, disorganised neuropil, and degeneration. It indicates that the cerebral cortex is damaged, possibly because of diabetic neurodegeneration, ischaemic injury, or neurotoxic damage. The results indicate the presence of gliosis and oedema, suggesting neuroinflammation or oxidative stress (score 3) (Fig. 1B).

In both Group 3 C and Group 4 D (treated groups), neuronal cell bodies are large, with visible nuclei, while glial cells have smaller, less transparent nuclei. There are no obvious signs of abnormal behaviour, such as neuronal loss, spongiform changes, or cytoplasmic inclusions or aggregates, but there is mild gliosis (score 2) (Fig. 1C, D).

- A score of 0 indicates no brain damage.
- A score of 1 indicates more than 10% brain damage.
- A score of 2 indicates 20–30% brain damage.
- A score of 3 indicates 40–60% brain damage.
- A score of 4 indicates more than 60% brain damage (Fouad and Ahmed 2021). Both Boos et al. (2021) and Abozaid et al. (2025) employed an identical scoring system for brain tissue damage.

Figure 1. Histopathological section of the cerebral cortex processed with haematoxylin and eosin (H&E) stain, visualised under $\times 400$ magnification. **A.** Shows normal neuronal architecture in the healthy control group G1 (1. Glial cell, 2. Large neuron cell); **B.** Diabetic positive control group (G2) shows neuronal degeneration (1. Pyknosis, 2. Gliosis with gemistocytic change, 3. Oedema); **C, D.** Treated Groups 3 and 4 with TQ show (1. Neuron with nucleus, 2. Oedema, 3. Glial cell).

Discussion

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is accompanied by severe consequences that significantly impair patients' status and quality of life. These problems are commonly divided into two groups: macrovascular and microvascular. Each kind affects a different group of organs. To efficiently address and avert these challenges, an extensive understanding of them is crucial (Reynolds et al. 2023).

This study aimed to clarify the preventive benefits of TQ, a safe natural compound, in alleviating diabetes-related complications, including oxidative stress, cerebral cortical injury, impaired glycaemic control, and nociceptive dysfunction in diabetic rats.

Thymoquinone was highly effective at lowering glycaemic levels in diabetic rats. This study showed that TQ significantly decreased blood glucose levels in a dose-dependent manner in the treated groups compared to the untreated group. Prior studies (Kanter et al. 2009; Al-Sa et al. 2014; Sangi et al. 2015) attribute this effect mainly to enhanced insulin production and preservation of pancreatic β -cells, as corroborated by histological analysis. In a comparable context, Sankaranarayanan and Pari (2011) illustrated that TQ preserves β -cell functionality, while Abdullah (2017) suggested that its antidiabetic properties may arise from reduced hepatic gluconeogenesis. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is recognised to significantly increase serum malondialdehyde (MDA), a key marker of oxidative stress and lipid peroxidation (Sadri et al. 2017; Angie et al. 2024). This study demonstrated that following 6 weeks of TQ treatment (25 mg/kg and 50 mg/kg), blood MDA levels remained near normal, indicating that TQ is an effective antioxidant. This finding corroborates prior research demonstrating that TQ augments natural antioxidant defences and elevates glutathione (GSH), catalase (CAT), and superoxide dismutase (SOD), while reducing malondialdehyde (MDA) (Almatroodi et al. 2021; Hafez et al. 2024). Another study by Aarag et al. (2017) indicates that TQ enhances the antioxidant properties of metformin.

In streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetes mellitus (DM), significant nociceptive alterations are evident, as demonstrated by hot plate and tail immersion assays. This includes lower nociceptive thresholds, hyperalgesia, and allodynia, which are caused by central mechanisms such as NR2B phosphorylation, microglial activation, and increased spinal cord expression of transient receptor potential vanilloid 1 (TRPV1) and proinflammatory cytokines (Ismail et al. 2018).

This research demonstrated that administering TQ to diabetic rats significantly enhanced their thermal nociceptive responses in a dose-dependent manner. The tail immersion test indicated that higher TQ doses partially preserved nociceptive function, and the hot plate test, specifically licking behaviour, showed that 50 mg/kg provided significant protection against thermal hyperalgesia. While in jumping behaviour, both doses were significant-

ly effective. The delay in the last behaviour displayed a dose-dependent pattern. These findings align with earlier studies demonstrating TQ's antinociceptive effects, primarily attributed to its antioxidant properties and to its ability to restore endogenous antioxidant levels (Shipilov et al. 2016; Lutfi et al. 2021).

Thymoquinone has exhibited analgesic effects by modulating supraspinal opioid systems (Abdel-Fattah et al. 2000), while Bashir and Qureshi (2010) found that thymoquinone could relieve pain and stop pain signals from reaching the brain after a spinal cord injury. They confirmed the effects of thymoquinone through mechanical allodynia, heat-cold allodynia, or biochemical assays. Additional studies confirm its efficacy in alleviating neuropathic pain following spinal cord injury and diminishing neuroinflammation by inhibiting cyclooxygenase and lipoxygenase (El-Dakhakhny et al. 2002; Çelik et al. 2014).

Hyperglycaemia negatively affects the cerebral cortex, leading to neuronal degeneration, apoptosis, and structural alterations (Hernández-Fonseca et al. 2009; Selim and Selim 2013; Meng et al. 2017). This study showed that untreated diabetic rats had higher histopathological damage scores (score 3), whereas both the low- and high-dose TQ groups had lower scores (score 2). This supports the idea that TQ has a protective effect on the cerebral cortex through its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. These results support and extend prior research indicating that oxidative stress, mitochondrial disorders, and impairment of the blood-brain barrier are significant contributors to diabetes-related cortical damage (Kamboj and Sandhir 2011; Fatani et al. 2016; Ali et al. 2021).

One of the crucial histopathological features in the cerebral cortex of the untreated group was gliosis. It involves the activation and proliferation of glial cells, including astrocytes and microglia, and constitutes a common pathological feature in the cerebral cortex of rats subjected to various traumas and disorders. This responsive process may involve cellular hypertrophy, increased glial fibrillary acidic protein production in astrocytes, and microgliosis. It is posited that gliosis significantly impacts neuronal and nociceptive signalling, particularly in heat nociception (Lomako et al. 2023). Gliosis's role in thermal nociception is through its impact on neuroinflammation and the regulation of pain signalling pathways. To develop treatments for chronic pain and neurological disorders, it is necessary to understand how glial activation, neuroinflammation, and specific temperature-sensing pathways interact (Gazerani 2021). In contrast to the treated groups, which exhibit lower glial reactivity, the untreated group demonstrated a substantially higher level of gliosis. That was the finding of this study.

This finding is in agreement with Jakaria et al. (2018), who concluded that in an STZ-induced diabetes model, pretreatment with TQ significantly diminishes the elevated concentrations of nitric oxide (NO) and MDA in the rat's brain relative to the control group.

Regarding histopathological alterations in the cerebral cortex, one study agrees with our result and concluded that *Nigella sativa* oil exhibited significant neuroprotective and neurorestorative effects in rats with streptozotocin-induced diabetes. It prevented structural neuronal damage in the cerebral cortex. Histopathological analysis of their study indicated a decrease in neuronal degeneration and a restoration of damaged neural tissues, implying that *Nigella sativa* possesses both preventive and therapeutic efficacy against diabetes-induced cerebral damage (Sangi and Jalaud 2019), while disagreeing with Aktas and Gur (2021), who documented an absence of histological alterations subsequent to TQ therapy, suggesting conflicting data, possibly due to the short duration of diabetes.

To our knowledge, no other studies have examined thymoquinone's ability to protect the cerebral cortex in diabetic rat models. Besides diabetes, several studies demonstrate TQ's ability to protect brain tissue from neurotoxicity and oxidative stress induced by ischaemia, pharmaceuticals, and chemicals (Kanter 2010; Mahmoud et al. 2019; Bilgiç et al. 2022; Ceylan et al. 2023). The data suggest that TQ preserves neuronal integrity and mitigates neurodegeneration; however, additional studies are required to verify its precise role in protecting the cerebral cortex in diabetic contexts.

Conclusion

Thymoquinone significantly improved hyperglycaemia regulation and reduced oxidative stress in diabetic rats. These effects were accompanied by pain alleviation and the maintenance of the cerebral cortex's structure. The findings indicate that TQ has systemic and neuroprotective advantages, making it a viable treatment for diabetes and associated neurological consequences.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

This work has been approved by the ethics committee of the college and university, with approval number Meeting code: 8, paper code: 1. Throughout this research work, all procedures were performed in accordance with the ARRIVE (Animal Research: Reporting In Vivo Experiments) guidelines.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: This work has been approved by the ethics committee in the College of Medicine, Hawler Medical University, with approval number Meeting code: 8, paper code 1. Throughout this research work, all procedures were performed in accordance with the ARRIVE (Animal Research: Reporting In Vivo Experiments) guidelines.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

KD: Conceptualization, data analysis, manuscript revision and supervision. NJA: Methodology, investigation, data interpretation, and data acquisition, manuscript writing. All authors revised the article critically for important intellectual content and approved for final version of manuscript.

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Data availability

The datasets used or analysed for the current study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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